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PEDAGOGICAL STRATEGIES FOR DIFFERENTIATED WRITING INSTRUCTION: ENHANCING STUDENT LEARNING

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Abstract: *This article explores the evolving significance of writing in foreign language education, emphasizing its role in communication and language skill development. It discusses the challenges of teaching writing effectively and proposes a differentiated approach to address diverse student needs. Drawing from linguistic and educational theories, the text delineates the concept of differentiation and its application in tailoring instruction to individual learners. Highlighting the importance of coherence, grammar, spelling, and language register in writing, it suggests six strategies for effective teaching, emphasizing the integration of language and task-based instruction. By incorporating modelled and shared writing techniques, educators can engage students in meaningful language practice and support their development as proficient writers. This comprehensive approach aims to equip students with the necessary skills to succeed in writing tasks while promoting academic growth and success in foreign language learning.*

Key words: *Coherence, grammar, spelling, differentiation, teaching, modelled writing, scaffolding techniques, skill level, learning style, academic growth.*

Introduction

Writing used to be ignored when teaching foreign languages, and most students didn't like it. But now, people see it as important for communication, just like speaking. Writing should connect to real-life needs and be taught with both language and tasks in mind. Learning to write well not only helps you write better, but also helps you learn other language skills, like choosing the right words and organizing your thoughts. This article talks about writing as a skill and suggests six ways to teach it effectively by focusing on both language and tasks.

According to Isabela Anda Dragomir, teaching writing is a tough task, involving coherence, grammar, spelling, and language register. Good writing at any level requires discovery, planning, creativity, and revision. To excel, students need to learn various techniques and approaches to writing tasks systematically. Different theories advocate structured methods like modelled and shared writing to engage students effectively. These methods involve teacher demonstration, student involvement, and language

practice. [1] The text highlights the complexities and challenges involved in teaching writing effectively, emphasizing the importance of various components such as coherence, grammar, spelling, and language register. To address these challenges, a differentiation approach can be employed to cater to the diverse needs and abilities of students.

What is differentiation?

The root of "differentiation" is "differentiate," which comes from the Latin word "differentia," meaning "difference" or "distinction." In its original sense, "differentiate" refers to the process of making or becoming different or distinct. According to Cambridge dictionary "differentiation" is the process or fact of being different or making something different from other similar things. Educational meaning refers that the use of different teaching materials and methods within the same lesson to suit the abilities and needs of different students. [2] This concept has been adopted across various fields, including mathematics, biology, and education, where it denotes processes, such as finding rates of change, cellular specialization, or modifying instruction to meet individual needs, respectively.

Differentiation in education refers to the practice of modifying instruction, content, and assessment to meet the diverse needs of individual learners. It involves tailoring teaching strategies, materials, and activities to accommodate variations in students' readiness, interests, and learning profiles. The goal of differentiation is to ensure that all students, regardless of their background or ability level, have access to meaningful and challenging learning experiences that promote academic growth and success.

In the context of teaching writing, differentiation involves tailoring instruction to meet the individual needs of students, considering factors such as their skill level, learning style, and interests. Differentiation recognizes that students have varying levels of proficiency in writing and may require different strategies and support to improve.

When applying a differentiation approach to teaching writing, educators can employ a variety of techniques to engage students effectively. For example, they can provide differentiated instruction by offering various writing tasks that accommodate different skill levels and learning styles. Additionally, educators can use scaffolding techniques to support students as they develop their writing skills, providing guidance and feedback based on individual needs.

Furthermore, a differentiation approach to teaching writing acknowledges that students may benefit from different instructional methods and approaches. Therefore, educators can incorporate diverse teaching strategies, such as modelled and shared

writing, to cater to the needs of all students. These structured methods involve teacher demonstration, student involvement, and language practice, providing students with opportunities to learn and apply writing techniques in a supportive environment.

Literature review

Rema Menon, (2015) carried out a study between 5th grade students on new methodology to differentiate instructional strategies for ESL learners in the Indian context. The study focused on using differentiated instruction and multiple assessments such as Informal Reading Inventory (IRI), Qualitative Spelling Inventory (QSI), Running Records, Dynamic Indicators of Basic Early Literacy Skills (DIBELS), High-frequency words and phonological awareness. Differentiating instruction and using small group instruction assisted and improved students' reading and writing proficiency. 94% of the students improved their reading comprehension by a minimum of three grade levels.

Naj Abdullah, (2015) investigated a study the effect of differentiated learning method on students' achievement in writing skills on learning Arabic as a foreign language. It was indicated that DLM method improves student's writing achievement in learning Araboic Language for Malaysian secondary school students.

Mona Smadi (2018) conducted a study on the Effectiveness of Using Differentiated Education Strategy in Developing the Literacy Skills of the Seventh Grade Students in English at Public Schools in Jordan. The authors focused on the experimental method to identify the effectiveness of differentiated education strategy in the development of literacy skills of seventh grade students in English at public schools in Jordan.

Jehona Rexhi Iljazi (2021) explored a study Effects of different approaches to writing on the improvement of students' writing performance. It was found that different approaches motivated students' writing skills and has been tested before and after test, the students' writing skill has been raised successfully with integrated teaching: controlled and free writing. Research suggested free writing than controlled teaching. As teachers have some challenges on controlled teaching.

Fatma Sari (2023) conducted a survey among students on implementing differentiated instruction in writing procedure. The research outlined that a significant difference in students' writing ability through the implementation of DI compared to connectional teaching methods.

The findings from multiple studies indicate that implementing differentiated instructional strategies positively impacts students' language skills across various contexts. In Rema Menon's study, differentiated instruction and small group instruction significantly improved reading and writing proficiency among 5th-grade ESL learners

in India. Naj Abdullah's research revealed that differentiated learning methods enhanced writing achievement in Arabic as a foreign language for Malaysian secondary school students. Mona Smadi's study demonstrated the effectiveness of differentiated education strategies in developing literacy skills among seventh-grade students in English in Jordan. Jehona Rexhi Iljazi found that integrated teaching approaches, particularly free writing, led to successful improvements in students' writing skills. Lastly, Fatma Sari's survey highlighted a significant difference in students' writing abilities through the implementation of differentiated instruction compared to conventional teaching methods. Overall, these findings underscore the importance and effectiveness of differentiated instructional approaches in promoting language skill development among students.

Conclusion

This article underscores the crucial role of writing in foreign language education and advocates for a differentiated approach to teaching it effectively. By recognizing the diverse needs and abilities of students and tailoring instruction accordingly, educators can foster meaningful language practice and support the development of proficient writers. Through the integration of language and task-based instruction, coupled with modelled and shared writing techniques, students are provided with valuable opportunities to enhance their writing skills and succeed in language learning. Embracing this comprehensive approach not only equips students with the necessary linguistic tools for effective communication but also promotes their academic growth and success in foreign language education.

REFERENCES

1. Isabela Anda DRAGOMIR, DIFFERENT APPROACHES TO DEVELOPING WRITING SKILLS, Land Forces Academy Review, Vol. XXV, No 3(99), 2020
2. Cambridge Dictionary, <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/us/dictionary/english/differentiation>
3. Naj Abdullah, The effect of differentiated learning method on students' achievement in writing skills in learning arabic as a foreign language, August, 2015
4. Mona Smadi, Effectiveness of Using Differentiated Education Strategy in Developing the Literacy Skills of the Seventh Grade Students in English at Public Schools in Jordan, 2018
5. Jehona Rexhi Iljazi, Effects of different approaches to writing on the improvement of students' writing performance, 2021
6. Fatma Sari, Implementing Differentiated Instruction in Writing Procedure Text for Grade X Students (Phase E) at SMA N 1 Wonosari, Indonesia, July 10, 2023.